

Dyes Derived from Substituted Phthalic Acids. Part I. $\Delta^{2,6}$ -Dihydrophthalic and *trans*- $\Delta^{3,5}$ -Dihydrophthalic Acids. Effect of Decreasing Unsaturation in the Phthalic Acid Portion of Phthalein Dyes

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$\Delta^{2,6}$ -Dihydrophthalic and *trans*- $\Delta^{3,5}$ -dihydrophthalic acids have been condensed with different phenols; the phthaleins obtained have been studied and compared with phthaleins from phthalic acid. The resorcinol-phthaleins have also been brominated and acetylated. The effect of decreasing unsaturation in the phthalic acid portion of the phthalein dyes has been observed.

$\Delta^{2,6}$ -Dihydrophthalic acid (I) and *trans*- $\Delta^{3,5}$ -dihydrophthalic acid (II) were condensed with resorcinol, orcinol, phenol, phloroglucinol, pyrogallol, catechol, quinol, and *o*-cresol to obtain different phthaleins. The resorcinol compounds were brominated and acetylated. The dyestuffs thus obtained were analysed and the respective phenolphthaleins were studied spectrophotometrically. The absorption maxima obtained have been compared with those of phthaleins from phthalic acid.

The phthaleins obtained are of the following types:

Type I(a) from acid (I):

Type I(b) from acid (II):

III(a) and III(b) : $R^1 = R^2 = R^4 = H$; $R^3 = -OH$.

IV(a) and IV(b) : $R^1 = Me$; $R^2 = R^4 = H$; $R^3 = -OH$.

V(a) and V(b) : $R^1 = R^3 = -OH$; $R^2 = R^4 = H$.

VI(a) and VI(b) : $R^1 = R^2 = H$; $R^3 = R^4 = -OH$.

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VII(a) and VII(b)	: R ¹ = R ² = R ³ = H; R ⁴ = -OH.
VIII(a) and VIII(b)	: R ¹ = R ³ = R ⁴ = H; R ² = -OH.
IX(a) and IX(b)	: R ¹ = H; R ² = R ⁴ = -Br; R ³ = -OH.
X (a) and X(b)	: R ¹ = R ² = R ⁴ = H; R ³ = -OCOMe.

Type 2(a) from acid (I):

Type 2(b) from acid (II):

XI(a) and XI(b) : R¹ = -OH; R² = H.

XII(a) and XII(b) : R¹ = -OH; R² = Me,

A comparative study of the absorption maxima of the compounds (phthaleins) shows that the changes in the lower portion of the phthalein dyestuffs (decreasing unsaturation in the phthalic acid portion) do not affect the light absorption to any great extent.

Probably the replacement of a double bond by a single one in the phthalic acid portion does not appreciably affect the charge that migrates between the two aromatic nuclei in the upper portion of the phthalein molecule as in the case of triphenylmethane and other dyes, where the central carbon atom can take part in the resonating system or in forming mesomeric states and consequently affects the migrating charge.

Thus, decreasing unsaturation in the phthalic acid portion of phthaleins has no appreciable effect on the value of absorption maximum wave length. Variations are only in the intensity of colour. The phthaleins from $\Delta^{3,5}$ -dihydrophthalic acid have more colour intensity than phthaleins from either phthalic acid or from $\Delta^{2,6}$ -dihydrophthalic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

$\Delta^{2,6}$ -Dihydrophthalic (I) and *trans*- $\Delta^{3,5}$ -dihydrophthalic (II) acids were prepared by the methods of Baeyer¹, melting respectively at 215° and 210°. The phthaleins of the type 1 (a and b) were obtained as follows:

The acids (I and II) were condensed with different phenols at different temperatures using H₂SO₄ (conc.) as the condensing agent (Table I). The condensed products, after cooling, were extracted with dilute NaOH and filtered. The phthaleins were precipitated by adding HCl (dilute) to the alkaline filtrates. The crude phthaleins obtained were purified by a second precipitation and crystallisation from ethanol. The crystalline products were dried at 100-110°.

1. Baeyer, *Annalen*, 1890, 250, 145; 1892, 269, 145.

TABLE I

Phthaleins.	Conditions for condensation.		M.P. Appearance. (Crystalline).	Colour: in		Formulas.		% Hydrogen.			
	Acid.	Phenol.		H ₂ SO ₄ Temp. & duration. (drops).	EtOH soln.	EtOH + alkali.	Found.		Reqd.		
III (a) Resorcinol- Δ ^{2,6} -DPH	I (2g.)	Resorcinol (3g.)	180-90° 3 hrs.	222° Yellowish brown	Yellow-green; Intense yellow fluorescent green	Yellow	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ O ₃	71.7	71.85	4.2	4.19
III (b) Resorcinol- Δ ^{3,5} -DPH	II (2g.)	"	180-90°; 3 hrs	265° Dark brown	Red-green; fluorescent	Yellow	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₃	71.6	71.85	4.3	4.19
IV (a) Orcinol- Δ ^{2,6} -DPH	I (1g.)	Orcinol (1.6g.)	160-70°; 3 hrs.	205° Brick-red	Do	Do	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₃	72.8	72.92	5.0	4.97
IV (b) Orcinol- Δ ^{3,5} -DPH	II (1g.)	Orcinol (1.6g.)	160-70°; 3 hrs.	220° Do	Do	Do	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₃	72.7	72.92	4.9	4.97
V (a) Phloroglucinol- Δ ^{2,6} -DPH	I (2g.)	Phloroglucinol (3g.)	190-200°; 3 hrs.	> 300° Do	Deep red	Do	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₇	65.4	65.57	3.9	3.82
V (b) Phloroglucinol- Δ ^{3,5} -DPH	II (2g.)	"	190-200°; 3 hrs.	> 300° Dark red	Do	Do	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₇	65.3	65.57	3.86	3.82
VI (a) Pyrogallol- Δ ^{2,6} -DPH	I (2g.)	Pyrogallol (3g.)	190-200°; 3 hrs.	> 300° Black	Yellowish brown	Dark brown	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₇	63.2	65.57	3.85	3.82
VI (b) Pyrogallol- Δ ^{3,5} -DPH	II (2g.)	Pyrogallol (3g.)	190-200°; 3 hrs.	> 300° Dark brown	Dark brown • Violet, fades	Dark brown • Violet, fades	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₇	65.3	65.57	3.86	3.82
VII (a) Catechol- Δ ^{2,6} -DPH	I (2g.)	Catechol (3g.)	190-200°; 3 hrs.	> 300° Black	Brown	Red-brown, fades	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₃	71.6	71.85	4.23	4.19
VII (b) Catechol- Δ ^{3,5} -DPH	II (2g.)	Catechol (3g.)	190-200°; 3 hrs.	> 300° Dark brown	Dark brown	Do	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₃	71.8	71.85	4.20	4.19
VIII (a) Quinol- Δ ^{2,6} -DPH	I (2g.)	Quinol (3g.)	190-200°; 3 hrs.	270° Black	Brown	Do	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₃	71.8	71.85	4.25	4.19
VIII (b) Quinol- Δ ^{3,5} -DPH	II (2g.)	Quinol (3g.)	190-200°; 3 hrs.	> 300° Dark brown	Yellowish brown	Do	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₃	71.56	71.85	4.23	4.19

TABLE I (contd.)

Phthalate.	Conditions for condensation.		M.P.	Appearance. (Crystalline).	Colour in EtOH soln. EtOH + alkali.	Formula.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.			
	Acid.	Phenol.					H ₂ SO ₄ (drops).	Temp. & duration.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
XI (a) Phenol- Δ ^{3,6} -DPH	I (3g.)	Phenol (6g.)	8 115-20°; 10 hrs.	244°	White	Colorless	Deep pink	C ₃₀ H ₁₆ O ₄	74.8	75.00	5.10	5.00
XI (b) Phenol- Δ ^{3,5} -DPH	II (3g.)	Phenol (6g.)	8 115-20°; 10 hrs.	170°	Brownish white	Almost colorless	Do	C ₃₀ H ₁₆ O ₄	74.7	75.00	5.05	5.00
XII (a) o-Cresol- Δ ^{3,6} -DPH	I (3g.)	o-Cresol (6g.)	10 110-15°; 12 hrs.	155°	Do	Do	Purple pink	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₄	75.6	75.86	5.70	5.74
XII (b) o-Cresol- Δ ^{3,5} -DPH	II (3g.)	o-Cresol (6g.)	10 105-10°; 14 hrs.	148°	Do	Do	Do	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₄	75.7	75.86	5.71	5.74

N. B. DPH: dihydrophthalatein. (d) : decomposes.

TABLE II

Phthalatein.	M.P.	Cryst. appearance.	Color in		Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
			EtOH soln.	EtOH + alkali.			
IX (a) Tetrabromoresorcinol- Δ ^{3,6} -DPH*	200°	Red	Purple-green	Intense purple-green	C ₃₀ H ₁₀ O ₅ Br ₄	Br : 49.0%	49.9%
IX (b) Tetrabromoresorcinol- Δ ^{3,5} -DPH	220°	Dark red	Pink-green	Intense pink-green	C ₃₀ H ₁₀ O ₅ Br ₄	Br : 48.9	49.2
X (a) Resorcinol- Δ ^{3,6} -DPH	155°	Brown	Brown	Brown	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₇	C : 68.0 H : 4.35	68.0 4.3
X (b) Resorcinol- Δ ^{3,5} -DPH	235°	Do	Do	Do	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₇	C : 68.7 H : 4.38	68.0 4.3

*DPH: dihydrophthalatein.

The phthaleins of the Type 2 (a and b) were obtained slightly in a different way, as follows:

The acid (I or II) was heated with an excess of the phenol (phenol or *o*-cresol) at 105° to 120° in presence of H₂SO₄ (conc.) for longer durations (Table I). The condensed semi-solid mass was poured in 50 to 75 ml of water and the excess of phenol removed by steam distillation. The residue was extracted with a dilute solution of NaOH and filtered. The crude phthalein was precipitated by adding HCl (dilute) to the alkaline filtrate. This was then purified by decolorising with animal charcoal (in ethanolic solution) and crystallised from ethanol-water (1:1) mixture. The properties of these phthaleins are recorded in Table I.

The resorcinol compounds (IIIa and IIIb) were brominated, using the method of Baeyer². The resulting tetrabromophthaleins (Table II) were crystallised from ethanol and dried at 110°.

The resorcinolphthaleins (IIIa and IIIb) were also acetylated, using acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate, and the diacetates (Table II) obtained were crystallised from ethanol and dried at 110°.

The absorption maxima ($\lambda_{\max}$) of the compounds prepared were determined in neutral and alkaline ethanolic solutions (Tables III and IV), using "British Unicam" spectrophotometer³. The maxima for phthaleins from phthalic anhydride were also determined using the same apparatus under similar conditions.

TABLE III
 $\lambda_{\max}$ in alkaline ethanolic solutions.

Phenols.	Phthaleins.	$\Delta^{2,6}$ -Dihydrophthaleins.	$\Delta^{3,5}$ -Dihydrophthaleins.
Resorcinol	500 m μ (fluorescein)	495 m μ	500 m μ
Orcinol	500 (orcein)	498	510
Phenol	560 (phenolphthalein)	560	560
Phloroglucinol	470	480	470
<i>o</i> -Cresol	570	575	573
Tetrabromoresorcinol	525 (eosin)	525	530
Pyrogallol	..	420 and 510	..

TABLE IV
 $\lambda_{\max}$ of a few phthaleins in neutral ethanolic solutions.

Phenols.	$\Delta^{2,6}$ -Dihydrophthaleins.	$\Delta^{3,5}$ -Dihydrophthaleins.
Resorcinol	450 m μ	460 m μ
Orcinol	450	450
Tetrabromoresorcinol	530	530
Phloroglucinol	430	445

The authors express their sincere thanks to Dr. S. Ghosh, Head of the Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, for providing necessary facilities.